

EARLY INTERVENTION STRATEGIES BY PARENTS AND TEACHERS OF CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL NEEDS

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Early Intervention Strategies by Parents and Teachers of Children with Special Needs

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Abstract

This study explored the early intervention strategies by parents and teachers of children with special needs. Using a qualitative methodology, specifically the narrative enquiry approach, the data were gathered from 10 participants through an in-depth interview. The ten participants were purposely selected based on the following inclusion criteria, for teachers: regular-permanent SPED teachers, with at least one year of teaching experience in SPED, and for parents, they have an autistic child enrolled in SPED. The data were recorded, transcribed, validated, and analyzed using Creswell's method of analyzing lived experiences. These data revealed four themes, namely: (1) Opening Doors: Strategies for Early Language Intervention for Children with Special Needs, (2) Empowering Connections: Effective Early Intervention Strategies for Special Needs Children's Social Skills, (3) Emotional Empowerment: Early Intervention Strategies for Promoting Emotional Well-being in Children with Special Educational Needs, (4) Early Steps to Self-Efficiency: Early Intervention strategies for SPED Children's Self-Help Skills. Each theme has its subtheme and is discussed thoroughly. Recommendations point to the need to implement an educative process which is collaborative and cooperative effort. Every sector has to take responsibility and commit so that the child receives the education he rightfully deserves. May this undertaking open more frontiers for children with special needs, and in the near future, there will be additional studies and research to the other levels and kinds of "being special".

Keywords: early intervention strategies, emotional skills, children with special needs, self-help skills, self-help skills

Introduction

inherent right also to education (United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund, 2016). This particular fact allows and empowers children to take part in educational processes that are cohesively planned to address various levels of giftedness. The role of social recognition, which vastly includes their participation to the teaching-learning process has a lifetime effect in the self-esteem of individuals with intellectual disability (Journal of Intellectual Disability, 2020). Children with special needs and who come from all levels of socio-demographic classes should be active participants to teaching and learning as provided for in inclusive education.

In the United States and other developed countries, the provision of comprehensive early intervention and support for children with developmental delays remains to be a high priority. This measure can, at minimum, help prevent the substantial decline in intellectual development that generally occurs across the early childhood period for children with development delays (Guralnick, 2017). Notwithstanding the fact that lower and middle-resourced countries are facing unique challenges in terms of financial resources, their efforts to and potential contributions of early intervention to children's development and family well-being for vulnerable children in general are well-recognized by the international community (World Health Organization & UNICEF, 2012). On the other hand, when early intervention strategies are not properly accorded to, these constraints influence downstream developmental processes resulting in specific child competencies (Elsabbagh & Smith, 2012, as cited in Guralnick, 2017).

In one of the central schools in Escalante City, teachers and parents were implementing intervention strategies, however the strategies utilized are not properly documented. These resulted to learning losses and possible learning gaps because interventions should be comprehensive and systematic. Special education, in the very first place, should involve the family, since it is the child's immediate environment and the family members provide him contact on a daily basis (Weiner, L., Togliola, J.P., and Girolani, G., 2019). The involvement of the family, their routines, and rituals, contribute a lot and has a lasting impact to children with disabilities (Education and Treatment of Children, 2019).

In developing countries, children with special needs have to contend with what is available to them and for them, in the process, disenfranchising them with the intervention that suit their level of giftedness and being special. Social media have been abuzz with success stories of children with special needs. They can accomplish anything and everything if timely and relevant intervention is accorded to them and accessible too. With these as basis, the researcher is fully motivated to conduct research about early intervention by parents and teachers of children with special needs.

Methodology

Research Design. This study qualifies as qualitative since the researcher investigated the participants' perceptions of early intervention strategies used by special needs children's parents and teachers. In-depth meaning and the fundamentally lived experiences that are founded in the sociocultural context of the subjects are mostly collected through qualitative research. It places the researcher in a situation where they can study the phenomenon. In order to examine phenomena without changing the context in which they arise, it encompasses a natural, holistic, and inductive process (Oliveros, 2020).

Respondents of the Study. The goal of this study was to identify the early intervention methods utilized by parents and teachers of

children with special needs. Five parents and five regular, permanent SPED instructors from one of Escalante City's central schools participated in this study for the academic year 2022–2023.

Data Gathering Procedure. By following the ethical guidelines, the researcher got the participants' consent before proceeding with the study. The researcher sent a letter to the research participants explaining the significance and importance of the study. During the meetings, the field notes recorded the participants' facial expressions, gestures, annotations, emphasis, pauses, and silence. The researcher conducted a recorded virtual face-to-face interview.

Data Analysis. The transcription of the audio-recorded interviews served as the foundation for the data analysis. Using (Creswell, 2014) six phases in data analysis and interpretation, the data were explained to reflect the essence of the early intervention tactics used by parents and teachers of children with special needs in this study.

Results and Discussion

This study aims to provide early intervention strategies to children with special needs, autism spectrum disorder (ASD) particularly. The respondents of this study are the parents themselves and the teachers as they go through the challenges, difficulties, and overall dynamics of having greatly involved in the lives of children with ASD. The early intervention strategies by parents and teachers of children with special needs in Escalante City, Negros Occidental, have four main themes which describe their early intervention strategies.

Theme 1: Opening Doors: Strategies for Early Language Intervention for Students with Special Needs

The early language intervention for this theme provides a clear path for children with special needs to follow in terms of their early language development. It encourages a child's capacity for emotional expression, communication, and comprehension. Additionally, it aids in the development and maintenance of relationships and the thinking abilities of the child. The foundation for children's reading and writing abilities as they begin and advance through school is laid by language development.

Subtheme 1: The Power of Pictures: Enhancing Language Learning Through Visuals. A child with special needs has to be able to communicate in order to better grasp their environment, daily life, and the challenges of adjusting at home and at school. Since pictures are all around us, they can also unlock a lot of things. As a result, if parents, guardians, and teachers know how to use pictures to connect them to real experiences, their emotions, interactions, routines, and literacy, they can also unlock the ability to communicate for a child with special needs. Speech, language, and communication play a crucial role throughout our lives, assisting us in understanding what is happening around us, according to the research Sword (2020). Three teachers emphasized the importance of using pictures in teaching their children. Printed and colored pictures can capture the learner's attention and concluded that language through visuals is a useful strategy of early intervention for students with special needs, particularly in their language development.

Subtheme 2: Singing the ABCs and Solving Puzzles: A Fun Approach to Language Development. The language of the soul is songs. They are manifestations of life, death, victories, losses, fear, love, courage, frustration, and anger, as well as adoration and appreciation to our All-Powerful God. Songs can assist a youngster with special needs in expressing his feelings and emotions, no matter how raw they may be. Songs can aid students in improving their listening abilities. When used properly, music is a potent educational tool. Children may be inspired and encouraged to pick up new words and memorize them. It can help children's brains grow, foster their creativity, increase their linguistic abilities, and facilitate better communication with others. It is also a healthy way for them to let out tension. Martin (2020) stated that music is a tool for having a great memory. While employed properly, while learning the ABCs, music has a way of "sticking" with us through melodies and a diversity of sounds. She continued by saying that music enhances language development, stimulates the brain, provides a creative outlet, and can help relieve stress. MV indicated that puzzles could also be of great help for children to improve their skills in understanding. Not only music can help learners in learning development but also play puzzles. Playing puzzles is not only for fun but can also develop visual reasoning and improve short-term memory and problem-solving skills.

Subtheme 3: Eyes on the Prize: Enhancing Language Fluency Through Clear and Deliberate Speaking. The ability to link language, emotion, and other bodily motions is possessed by our eyes. When we understand the dynamics of eye movements, social interactions, romantic relationships, and language abilities become natural. The eyes are also known as the windows of the soul. Improving language proficiency through intentional and clear speaking. Children imitate adults. Teachers must ensure that when we teach our children words and vocabulary, it must be correct word pronunciation, not baby talk. Let them repeat the words properly and speak slowly and clearly so that it could not be difficult for them to repeat the same words. Give them opportunities to respond by leaving pauses after your sentences.

Since children frequently learn through observation and imitation of adults, as indicated by (Sword,2021), make sure that you are modeling strong speech and language skills as much as you can. Speaking quietly and clearly while speaking slowly gives them time to comprehend the information. Not using "baby words"; children will need to learn the adult way of communicating, and if you model it for them, they'll learn it more quickly. Modeling the proper pronunciation and sentence structure.

Subtheme 5: Small Steps to Big Language: Introducing Simple Words Before Complex Ones. For children with special needs,

something big all starts with small ones. The facility of communication all commences with very simple words, connected as much as possible to his daily routines and interactions.” Bu specified that they used simple words, not complicated ones. BU also quoted that she uses complete words. Children are first introduced to a concept or idea in its simplest form as they progress and become able to make more complex connections. It should be in complete words or sentences. According to Montessori, infants are introduced to concepts and ideas in their most basic forms first. As they advance and improve their ability to make more intricate connections. A guideline for how presentations is presented in a Montessori classroom. A concept or idea is first presented to children in its most basic form. They can eventually manage information that is less isolated as they develop and have the ability to make more complicated connections.

Theme 2: Empowering Connections: Effective Early Intervention Strategies for Special Needs Children's Social Skills.

In order to develop their social abilities, special needs children require relationships with peers. Children learn how to interact with people and communicate through these relationships. Making friends will support self-esteem and confidence growth. As a result of being empowered by their connections, they develop positive growth mindsets, follow their goals despite their limitations, and positively impact society as a whole.

Subtheme 1: Together We Stand: Encouraging Student Interaction to Boost Self-Esteem and Social Skills. Children with special needs learn through interaction and socialization because these two are a regular part of their everyday lives. Students who lack social skills shouldn't be made to feel guilty for their shortcomings. They require assistance as they age in order to be guided, given attention, helped to understand others, assisted in making decisions in life, and have positive relationships and connections with others around them. Maw, No, and MV shared the same idea that encouraging social interactions can boost self-esteem and social skills. Social interaction is essential and helps children build strong relationships, build trust, understand different feelings, build positive behaviors, learn new things, and develop socially and cognitively. Fitwi Dwi Arini et al. reference Gresham & Elliot, 1984 as supporting evidence. al., 2019) defined social skills as socially acceptable learned behaviors that let a person communicate with others in ways that elicit good responses and assist in avoiding negative reactions. Social skills are the abilities that allow us to interact positively with others. In addition, interpersonal skills should be cultivated. John Dewey is an advocate of experiential learning. Each child, in his opinion, was energetic, inquisitive, and eager to learn. He also thought that they all needed to engage with others and be able to work both independently and constructively with their peers and adults. As a result, people gain knowledge and experience from their past encounters and interactions with their environment. Individuals learn new concepts, ideas, practices, and knowledge as a result of these encounters, which are then refined by the learner's life experiences and social connections, according to John Dewey.

Subtheme 2: Talking Together: Using Pair-Share and Round Table to Enhance Social Skills. According to Vygotsky, social learning actually promotes cognitive development throughout life and is a necessary component of lifelong development. In other words, all learning tasks can be completed by students with the help of an adult or in collaboration with peers. The development of chances for students to work together with the teacher and peers in the construction of knowledge and understanding is supported by this notion. Since learning is focused on student contact, discussion, and idea sharing, the collaborative theory of social constructivism will support the instructors' position. According to Kapur (2018), the social creation of knowledge takes place in a variety of settings and on different scales. It might be attained through teamwork, discussion in groups, or any other type of educational engagement. Students develop the knowledge and experience necessary for leading fulfilling lives when they engage with others, the physical and immaterial world, and themselves. Teachers can effectively improve the social skills of students with special educational needs by having group discussions at round tables and pair-shares. They have the chance to feel more at ease speaking their minds thanks to this tactic. Additionally, it enhances pupils' listening and speaking abilities. Every pupil gains knowledge from their partners.

Subtheme 3: "Beyond the Classroom: Encouraging SPED Learners to Join School Activities and Sports.” People learn best by doing. Children with special needs will learn a lot and even succeed if they enjoy what they are doing. Numerous success stories of children with special needs showed that by being involved in extracurricular activities and sports, they were able to normalize their condition, and their talent was no longer an obstacle. The teachers underlined that they support students participating in extracurricular activities and athletics. They shouldn't confine themselves to the classroom's four walls. Participating in school sports and extracurricular activities fosters the development of teamwork, positive values, mental acuity, self-esteem, and confidence. According to a study by Barbu et al. (2020), giving kids different roles to play in team activities enables older individuals to reestablish social connections. Additionally, it encourages competition and self-improvement. Sport offers chances to interact with others, communicate, and learn new values like respect, tolerance, and fair play. Sports events also include a socializing component. They cause onlookers to exhibit psychological responses, feelings, emotions, and behaviors typical of athletes. According to Czupic (2020), sports should be viewed in a very broad context. It is a practice that has societal repercussions in addition to helping to improve health and well-being. It enables the development of not only individual growth but also that of regional communities and the entire society. It significantly affects how well people's lives are lived by having an impact on their bodily, emotional, and psychological states. It enhances integration, creates new chances for engagement and social inclusion, and as a result, it reduces or even eliminates many detrimental social impacts.

Subtheme 4: Together We Learn: Encouraging Successful Mainstreaming of SPED Learners. The formal schooling of children with special needs can do so much for them. If they are already capacitated inside the SPED-contained class, putting them in mainstream classes aptly allows them to slowly integrate with society in general. For students who successfully developed their conduct in the self-

contained class, two teachers suggested mainstreaming in the normal class. Educating special needs students in regular classes during set times based on their unique skills is known as mainstream. The DepEd Order No.044 s. 2021's Policy Guidelines on the Provision of Educational Programs and Services for Learners with Disabilities in the K–12 Basic Education Program made clear that all schools should strive to be inclusive and should provide a setting where all students can learn together, wherever possible, regardless of any difficulties or differences they may have. This includes ensuring that students with disabilities are included in mainstream or general education.

Subtheme 5: Adventures in Socialization: Bringing SPED Learners to Places for Social Interaction. People claim that visiting new areas helps to heal the mind and replenish one's energy. The benefits are substantially greater for a youngster with special needs than for the average person. Here, letting him interact and explore his neighborhood counts as travel in his eyes. “Parents mention that they encourage their kids to be exposed to the community so they can socialize and learn how to communicate with others. The enhancement of children's performance, self-esteem, and behavior is greatly aided by parental involvement in the social skill development of the child. Bariroh (2018) demonstrates the importance of the magnitude of parental involvement's impact on student's motivation and accomplishment. This is due to the fact that pupils' motivation may come from both internal and external sources. It is a dynamic process that results in behavior that is goal oriented. In order to improve children's motivation, it is therefore important to strengthen parental participation.

Subtheme 6: Playing Together: Encouraging SPED Learners to Play with Other Children. A youngster with special needs can benefit much by playing with other kids and interacting with them. Their ability to interact socially with others may improve. Youngsters can learn to express their feelings and exercise self-control through listening, paying attention, and sharing play experiences. Playing with other kids, in particular, can do wonders for a child with special needs. Their ability to interact socially with others may improve. Youngsters can better understand their emotions and learn self-control by listening, focusing, and sharing play experiences. According to two parents, they let their kids play with other kids every afternoon outside of their home. She is acting in her child's best interests. She has always felt comfortable discussing her child's predicament since she is accepted. Children can pick up new social skills and abilities through playing with others. The overall growth of your child depends on these abilities.

Play Theory postulates that as children play and role-play situations to come up with solutions, play is crucial to both language development and comprehension of the outside world. As they experiment, fail, receive feedback, modify their strategies, and try again, youngsters learn more through the social interaction of play. According to Dr. Montessori, "Play is the child's work." She suggested that play was essential for assisting kids in exercising choice, practicing, and perfecting actions, or activities. Additionally, allowing SPED students to play with other kids might help them develop their social skills, communication abilities, and ability to engage with others.

Theme 3: Emotional Empowerment: Early Intervention Strategies for Promoting Emotional Well-being in Children with Special Educational Needs.

Promoting the emotional health of kids with special needs lays a solid basis for their emotional growth and yields beneficial intrapersonal and interpersonal long-term effects. Additionally, it encourages youngsters to develop a healthy self-concept, respect for others, and a sense of well-being.

Subtheme 1: Discipline with Love: Building Healthy Habits through Proper Discipline. It has been stated and emphasized in the study that everything that we do for a child with special needs is and be all for our love for him, Discipline included. “Maw and No emphasized that Discipline is very important to impose on their child. Both good and negative effects can be seen on children's behavior and mental health when appropriate Discipline and regular care are used. Children's healthy development is required. Physical punishment, such as spanking, has been linked to increased aggression, antisocial behavior, and mental health issues in children, according to research by (Gershoff et al.,2018). Children who received more severe physical punishment also showed higher rates of anxiety, sadness, and low self-esteem, according to the study. “Mi mentioned that proper disciple using positive reinforcement would result in a positive impact on children's behavior. Mi mentioned that proper disciple using positive reinforcement would result in a positive impact on children's behavior. In a study conducted by Kazdin et al. (1987) found that positive reinforcement led to significant improvements in children's behavior and decreased the likelihood of future problem behaviors.

Subtheme 2: From Frustration to Connection: How Gestures Can Enhance Communication in SPED. As they say, actions speak louder than words. If this statement has a great impact on a normal person, how much more on a child with special needs? They convey their wants and feelings through gestures. According to one of the teacher responders, gestures can be an effective method for enhancing communication between people who have special educational needs (SPED) and others. With the help of gestures, people with SPED may be better able to interact with others and express themselves, which will help to improve communication and lessen frustration. Several studies have explored the use of gestures in SPED communication, providing support for this idea. For example, a study by (Rüegg and colleagues,2016) found that gesture-based communication interventions improved the communication skills of children with an autism spectrum disorder. Similarly. These results imply that gestures may also be an effective method for enhancing communication in SPED. The ability of people with SPED to connect with others and feel less frustrated may be improved by including more gestures in communication encounters. These results imply that gestures may also be an effective method for enhancing communication in SPED. The ability of people with SPED to connect with others and feel less frustrated may be improved by including

more gestures in communication encounters.

Subtheme 3: A Place at the Table: Ensuring Your SPED Child Feels Important in the Family Dynamic. Children with all levels of giftedness should be loved, should be cared for, should be acknowledged, should be treasured. These comments from the parents of our SPED students demonstrate the value of giving a child with special needs a sense of importance and belonging in their household. This can be difficult since parents of children with special needs frequently concentrate on the needs of the kid and may unwittingly miss the child's desire for inclusion and engagement in family life. Studies have shown that children with special needs who feel they have a place in their family dynamic have better outcomes in terms of socialization, emotional well-being, and overall quality of life. For example, a study by (Weiner, Toglia & Girolami,2019) found that parental support and communication were key factors in promoting a sense of belonging for children with developmental disabilities. It is essential for a child with special needs to have emotional health and a general quality of life so that they feel valued and included in their family's dynamic. Studies have indicated that parental involvement, open communication, and family activities can help these kids feel more a part of the family and enhance their outcomes.

Subtheme 4: Shining Moments: Celebrating Achievements of Students with Special Needs. Giving heaps of Praise to a child with special needs is one way to recognize that what he is doing is worthy of commendation; thus, it is his achievement. The importance of recognizing and applauding the successes of students with special needs is implied by the parent's reaction who a learner with special education needs. It emphasizes the premise that kids with special needs should be given the same opportunity as their counterparts without disabilities to demonstrate their talents, skills, and accomplishments. Several studies have shown that celebrating the achievements of students with special needs can have a positive impact on their self-esteem, motivation, and overall well-being. For example, a study conducted by (Yang and colleagues,2020) found that social recognition and acknowledgment of accomplishments improved the self-esteem of students with intellectual disabilities. Another study by Vaz and colleagues (2017) showed that recognizing the accomplishments of students with special needs can also increase their motivation and engagement in academic activities. In this study, the researchers found that acknowledging and celebrating achievements improved the academic performance of students with learning disabilities. Overall, recognizing and celebrating the achievements of students with special needs is an important step towards inclusive education and promoting their overall well-being.

Subtheme 5: Heartfelt Lessons: Imparting the Right Values to Children with Special Needs. This section of the study is crucial because appropriate behavior and politeness should support a child with special needs efforts in school and at home. Therefore, it is crucial that the adults in their immediate environment set an example of the right values, behavior, and manners. These quotes from our parent respondents imply that it is crucial to instill core values in children with special needs. They frequently experience a variety of issues, such as social isolation or communication problems, which can affect their confidence and self-esteem. Consequently, teaching them good values can be a very effective way to help them thrive in life and develop resilience. Several studies have shown that teaching values to children with special needs can have a positive impact on their lives. For example, a study by (Brown et al.,2012) found that teaching positive values such as kindness, respect, and empathy to children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) could lead to improved social skills, increased empathy, and reduced problem behavior. Therefore, educating children with special needs about good values might help them overcome obstacles and achieve in life. Teaching principles that enable special needs children to develop their self-esteem, social skills, and sense of self-determination should be a top priority for educators, parents, and caregivers. That children gradually attain to give them more independence. It's about learning life skills so they can look after themselves without depending on others.

Theme 4: Early Steps to Self-Sufficiency: Early Intervention Strategies for SPED Children's Self-Help Skills. Self-help skills are abilities that children gradually attain to give them more independence. It's about learning life skills so they can look after themselves without depending on others.

Subtheme 1: Inspiring Greatness: How Praise and Reward Can Encourage SPED Students to Thrive. Providing specialized education to individuals with special needs is a challenging but rewarding task for educators who aim to improve the lives of their learners. One of the key teachings that can equip them for a more meaningful and productive life is self-help skills training. These skills, which encompass basic daily living activities such as bathing, dressing, and grooming, empower learners with special education needs to gain independence, confidence, and self-reliance. Studies have shown that positive reinforcement, such as Praise and rewards, can improve the behavior and academic performance of SPED students. One study conducted by (Shogren et al.,2018) found that when teachers used positive reinforcement strategies with students with intellectual disabilities, there was a significant increase in on-task behavior, academic engagement, and academic achievement. However, it's essential to ensure that Praise and rewards are used appropriately. Overusing Praise or rewards can lead to a decrease in intrinsic motivation and may even have negative effects on self-esteem. It's important to use Praise and rewards to reinforce specific behaviors or accomplishments rather than simply praising a student for their general abilities.

Subtheme 2: Active Learning for All: The Importance of Learning by Doing in SPED Education. Three of our teacher respondents emphasized that it is essential to provide students with opportunities to actively engage with the material they are learning to enhance their learning outcomes and overall educational experience. Studies have shown that experiential learning, or learning by doing, can be particularly effective for SPED students. For example, a study conducted. Furthermore, a study by Cox et al. (2016) investigated

the effects of a hands-on science program on the academic achievement of students with disabilities. The study found that students who participated in the program showed significant improvements in their science knowledge and skills, as well as increased engagement and interest in science. Learning by doing can also be an effective way to promote independence and self-determination in SPED students. Furthermore, it is impossible to overestimate the value of experiential learning in SPED instruction. Learning by doing has an established track record of improving academic performance, social skills, communication, problem-solving abilities, and self-determination. Allowing learners, the opportunity to be actively involved in what they are learning can improve their educational experience and advance their success as a whole.

Subtheme 3: Playtime for Everyone: Adapting Toys for SPED Children's Success. Two of the parent respondents highlighted the importance of making playtime inclusive and accessible for children with special needs. Adapting toys and games to meet the unique needs of SPED children can enhance their play experience, increase engagement, and promote their overall development.

A study by (Armitage et al.,2014) investigated the use of inclusive playgrounds for children with disabilities. The study found that inclusive playgrounds provided opportunities for children with disabilities to engage in play with their peers and develop social skills. In addition, adapting toys and games for SPED children can enhance their play experience, increase engagement, and promote their overall development. Providing inclusive and accessible play opportunities can also help SPED children develop social skills and engage in play with their peers.

Subtheme 5: Step-by-Step Progress: Guiding SPED Children to Acquire Basic Skills. Parents play a crucial role in helping their children with special needs learn basic life skills, such as dressing, grooming, and cooking, which can promote their overall development and quality of life. "One parent specifies that guiding their children in acquiring basic skills is their obligation as a parent; gradually, the children will develop the skills. "The idea of parents guiding their children with special needs to fully learn basic life skills is essential in promoting independence and self-sufficiency. Several studies have shown that parental involvement in teaching life skills to children with special needs can have positive outcomes. For example, a study (Shogren et al., 2018) found that parental involvement in teaching life skills to adolescents with disabilities was associated with increased independence and self-determination skills. A study by (Parish et al., 2017) found that parents of children with disabilities who participated in a life skills training program reported decreased stress and increased confidence in their ability to support their children's development. To sum up, parental involvement in helping children with special needs learn life skills can benefit both the child and the parent. It can encourage a child's independence and autonomy, boost parental confidence, and lessen stress for everyone involved. Therefore, it is crucial to support and encourage parents as they help their special needs children fully acquire fundamental life skills.

Research Simulacrum

Figure 1. Simulacrum of Major Themes and Subthemes

This study utilized a descriptive qualitative approach in the Early Intervention Strategy of Teachers and Parents of Children with Special Needs in Escalante City, Negros Occidental. According to the recounting and narrative phrases of the participants in the interviews, the early intervention strategies by parents and teachers mentioned in Figure I are further enhanced with other concepts and ideas that further describe the early intervention strategies of teachers and parents of children with special needs. The early intervention strategies of teachers and parents of children with special needs in Escalante City, Negros Occidental, have four main themes which describe their early intervention strategies.

Conclusions

This study tackles the difficulties a special child undergoes amidst the stigma he receives on a daily basis. But beyond the struggles, relevant and timely interventions bring light at the end of the tunnel and provide hope to children with special needs. It may be useful to the parents, guardians, and teachers since the child's first classroom is his home, and the parents/guardians are his first teachers. When a child enters school, the teachers become his second parents. The recommended interventions contained in this study would greatly capacitate and empower the parents, guardians, and teachers on how to provide educational tools to children with special needs and make the school a place for development, renewal, and a haven of love, respect, self-worth, and hope.

This study may be helpful also to the Department of Education and Schools Division Office since they are directly involved in the planning, curriculum, and teacher recruitment. Even if a child is special or not, his education falls within the village. An African proverb aptly states that "it takes the whole village to educate a child. With this, the educative process is a collaborative and cooperative effort. Every sector of that village has to take responsibility and commit so that the child receives the education he rightfully deserves. My time will come when the Department of Education puts up more SPED Centers all over the country and in every public school, complete with the necessary facilities and equipment, together with teachers whose specialization is Special Education. In so doing, parents and guardians will be encouraged to send and enroll their children with special needs- a lifesaver indeed.

For this particular study, it would also be very helpful to the school administrators to implement the suggested strategies for the parents and teachers. Formal schooling should be underlined as an expression of love, care, patience, and perseverance. As a matter of fact, countless success stories of special children who became successful became who they are because of unconditional love, care, patience, and perseverance on the part of the parents, teachers, and the whole community.

Special children (ASD) autism spectrum disorder particularly needs formal schooling that the SPED Centers offer. They will be able to avail of educative procedures and interventions to further develop and hone his mental, linguistic, affective, psycho-social, and emotional well-being. Sports also contribute to boosting his self-esteem and social skills. Pictures mean a lot; singing the ABCs and solving puzzles helped establish language fluency and deliberate speaking.

To future researchers, this study is only limited to the interventions needed for ASD. Since no man is an island- we need to empower connections and be involved with each other. Their simple interaction with other children through play is very vital to boost their social skills and self-esteem. May this undertaking open more frontiers for children with special needs, and in the near future, there will be additional studies and research on the other levels and kinds of "being special."

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